

EFFECTIVE TECHNIQUES TO INCREASE STUDENTS’ COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM

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Abstract: The purpose of this study is to ascertain how much knowledge there is about new technologies, their applications, and their activities in language courses. To arrive at a consensus, the techniques are debated and contrasted. The high-level application of techniques utilized in English language instruction is the focus of this research article.

Key words: techniques, activities, professional education, effectively communicate, tourism professionals, students' communicative competence, Role-playing, Field-trips.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the ability to know foreign languages is becoming one of the integral parts of professional education. Due to the high rate of cooperation with foreign partners among specialists in various fields, their demand for language learning is high.

In the tourism industry, professionals need to effectively communicate with tourists from around the world. English is the global language of communication, and having a strong command of English enables tourism professionals to interact fluently with visitors, understand their needs, and provide them with a positive experience.

Tourism management faculties teach students specific industry-related terminology and vocabulary in English, which is essential for students to understand concepts, trends, and best practices within the field. This knowledge allows them to be more proficient in their jobs and excel in the tourism industry.

Professionals in tourism management often need to write reports, proposals, emails, and other documents in English. By improving their English writing skills through ESP courses, students can effectively convey their ideas, proposals, and research findings to a wider audience, both within the organization and externally.

As the tourism industry is a globalized sector, having a strong command of English provides students with a competitive edge in the job market. Employers in the tourism industry often prioritize candidates who are proficient in English as it demonstrates their ability to work in an international environment and effectively communicate with a diverse range of clients and colleagues.

METHODS and RESULTS

Learning English in the context of tourism management also helps students gain a better understanding of different cultures and customs, which is essential when working with international tourists. This cultural awareness enables professionals to provide a more personalized and respectful service to visitors, leading to increased customer satisfaction and loyalty.

English teachers must take into account the above important factors when conducting lessons in this direction and the techniques that are chosen by them should be very interesting and effective and enable to activate the students.

There are several effective techniques to increase students' communicative competence in the field of tourism and hotel management:

Role-Playing: Create scenarios where students can practice real-life communication situations that they may encounter in the industry, such as handling guest inquiries, making reservations, or dealing with customer complaints.

Role play is a valuable technique in English classes for Tourism Management students as it allows them to simulate real-life scenarios they may encounter in the industry.

For example, students can engage in a role play activity where they pretend to be hotel staff and guests, practicing language skills related to hotel reservations, check-in procedures, customer service interactions, and problem-solving. This activity can help students improve their English speaking, listening, and interpersonal

skills while also gaining a better understanding of the dynamics of the hospitality sector.

Through role play, students can enhance their ability to handle different situations that may arise in tourism settings, such as handling customer complaints, providing recommendations on tourist attractions, or managing hotel bookings. This hands-on approach helps students develop confidence in using English in professional contexts and prepares them for future roles in the tourism industry where effective communication is crucial.

Field Trips: Organize visits to hotels, tourist attractions, and other relevant sites to give students firsthand experience in using their language skills in a practical setting. This can help them develop confidence and fluency in communicating with guests and colleagues. Field trips are a valuable technique in English classes for Tourism Management students as they provide real-world experience and practical application of language skills in the tourism industry.

For instance, a field trip to a local tourist attraction, such as a museum or famous landmark, could be organized for students to practice speaking and listening skills in English. During the field trip, students can engage with tourists, guides, and staff members using English language skills to inquire about the history, significance, and visitor information related to the attraction.

By immersing themselves in an English-speaking environment during the field trip, students can enhance their communication skills, vocabulary, and cultural understanding necessary for working in the tourism industry. Additionally, the hands-on experience gained from the field trip can make the learning process more engaging and memorable for students.

Group Discussions: Encourage group discussions on relevant topics in the field of tourism and hotel management. This can help students practice their speaking and listening skills, as well as learn from each other's experiences and perspectives.

Group discussions are a beneficial technique in English classes for Tourism Management students as they allow for collaborative learning and the exchange of ideas related to the industry.

For example, students can participate in a group discussion on sustainable tourism practices and their impact on local communities and the environment. Each student can research and present their perspective on the topic, leading to a fruitful discussion where different viewpoints are shared and debated. This exercise can help students develop critical thinking skills, improve their English language proficiency, and gain a deeper understanding of the importance of sustainability in the tourism sector.

Group discussions can also focus on current trends in the tourism industry, such as the rise of ecotourism or the challenges posed by over tourism. By engaging in these discussions, students can expand their knowledge, practice expressing their opinions in English, and learn to listen and respond to their peers effectively. This interactive approach to learning facilitates a deeper engagement with the subject matter and encourages students to think critically about the issues facing the tourism industry today.

Language Games: Incorporate language games and activities into your lessons to make learning fun and engaging. Games like role-play simulations, vocabulary quizzes, and language puzzles can help students improve their language skills in an interactive way. The language game technique is a fun and interactive way to reinforce language skills in English classes for Tourism Management students. One example of using language games in the context of Tourism Management would be a game focused on vocabulary related to travel and tourism.

For example, students can play a game where they have to match travel-related words with their corresponding definitions or pictures. This game can help students expand their vocabulary and improve their understanding of key terms used in the tourism industry.

Another language game could involve creating a dialogue scenario where students have to act out different roles commonly found in hospitality settings, such as a hotel receptionist and a guest. This not only helps students practice their English speaking skills but also familiarizes them with the language and communication styles used in real-life tourism contexts. By incorporating language games into

English classes for Tourism Management, students can engage actively with the material, enhance their language proficiency, and have fun while learning. These games can provide a dynamic and enjoyable way to practice language skills specifically relevant to their future careers in the tourism industry.

Guest Speakers: Invite guest speakers from the tourism and hospitality industry to share their experiences and insights with students. This can provide valuable real-world context for language learning and inspire students to improve their communicative skills. Inviting guest speakers to English classes in Tourism Management can be a valuable technique to provide real-world insights and experiences to students. Guest speakers can offer industry expertise, share practical knowledge, and inspire students to learn more about the tourism industry.

For example, an English class focusing on tourism marketing could invite a guest speaker who is a seasoned marketing professional in the tourism sector. This speaker can share their experiences, provide case studies, and discuss current trends in tourism marketing. This not only enhances students' understanding of the subject but also allows them to learn from someone with hands-on experience in the field.

The next example could be inviting a guest speaker who has worked in international hospitality management to share their experiences and insights on cross-cultural communication in the tourism industry. This can help students understand the importance of effective communication and cultural awareness when interacting with guests from diverse backgrounds.

Guest speakers can also conduct workshops or interactive sessions to engage students in practical activities related to their expertise. For instance, a guest speaker specializing in sustainable tourism could lead a workshop on sustainable practices in the industry and challenge students to come up with innovative solutions for implementing sustainability in tourism businesses.

Multimedia Resources: Use multimedia resources such as videos, podcasts, and online articles related to tourism and hotel management to expose students to authentic language and situations. This can help them develop their listening and reading comprehension skills while also expanding their vocabulary.

Using multimedia resources in English classes in Tourism Management can enhance student engagement, facilitate interactive learning, and provide a dynamic way to explore various aspects of the tourism industry. Here's an example of how multimedia resources can be effectively incorporated into the classroom:

Interactive Virtual Tours: In an English class focusing on tourist destinations, teachers can utilize multimedia resources such as virtual tours to immerse students in different locations around the world. For example, students can virtually explore popular tourist attractions, hotels, or cultural sites using interactive platforms like Google Earth or virtual reality applications. This not only helps students visualize the destinations but also improves their language skills by describing the locations and sharing their experiences in English.

Video Case Studies: Teachers can use video case studies to illustrate real-life scenarios in the tourism industry. For instance, in a class discussing hospitality management, students could watch videos showcasing successful hotel management practices, customer service techniques, or destination marketing strategies. Watching these videos can provide students with practical insights and spark discussions on relevant topics in English, allowing them to analyze, debate, and apply their language skills in a professional context.

Online Tourism Blogs and Podcasts: Encouraging students to explore online tourism blogs, podcasts, and vlogs can be a valuable multimedia resource to supplement classroom learning. Students can listen to industry experts discussing trends, innovations, and challenges in the tourism sector, or read articles featuring travel experiences and tips. This not only exposes students to authentic English language materials but also broadens their knowledge of the tourism industry and fosters independent learning.

Interactive Language Learning Apps: Teachers can introduce interactive language learning apps tailored to the tourism sector to improve students' English language skills. Apps like Duolingo, Babbel, or Rosetta Stone offer specialized courses in tourism-related vocabulary, phrases, and communication skills. Students

can practice pronunciation, take quizzes, and engage in language exercises that are specifically relevant to careers in tourism management.

By incorporating these multimedia resources into English classes in Tourism Management, educators can create a dynamic and engaging learning environment that caters to different learning styles, enhances language proficiency, and provides valuable insights into the global tourism industry.

Case studies: Use real-life case studies from the tourism and hotel industry to give students practical examples of communication challenges they may face. This can help them learn how to analyze situations and develop effective communication strategies.

The case study technique is a valuable teaching method that can be applied in English classes for students studying Tourism Management. It involves presenting students with real-life scenarios or situations related to the tourism industry, and then analyzing and discussing them in a classroom setting.

Case Study: A resort in a popular tourist destination is facing challenges with environmental sustainability. The management team is struggling to balance the needs of eco-conscious travelers with the financial demands of running a profitable business. Students are presented with information about the resort, including its current sustainability practices, customer feedback, and financial performance.

Activity:

1. Divide students into small groups and assign roles such as resort manager, environmental consultant, marketing team, and local community representative.
2. Each group must analyze the case study, discuss the challenges faced by the resort, and develop a plan to improve its sustainability practices while maintaining profitability.
3. Groups present their recommendations to the class, explaining their rationale and potential outcomes.
4. Facilitate a class discussion where students can compare and contrast different solutions, identify the benefits and drawbacks of each approach, and explore the ethical considerations involved.

Benefits of using the case study technique:

1. Encourages critical thinking and problem-solving skills: Students are challenged to apply theoretical knowledge to real-world situations, fostering a deep understanding of key concepts.
2. Promotes active engagement and collaboration: Group discussions and presentations encourage students to work together, share ideas, and learn from each other's perspectives.
3. Enhances communication skills: Students practice expressing their thoughts clearly and persuasively, both verbally and in writing, which is essential for success in the tourism industry.
4. Provides practical insights: By analyzing actual cases from the field, students gain practical insights into the complexities and challenges of managing tourism businesses effectively.

Language Exchanges: Encourage students to participate in language exchange programs or conversation partners with native speakers in the tourism and hospitality industry. This can provide valuable opportunities for students to practice their language skills in a supportive and immersive environment.

DISCUSSION

By means of role-playing and other activities that mentioned above enable to activate students in English classes in Tourism management department and may augment their proficiency in managing many scenarios that may emerge in tourism environments, such as resolving customer grievances, offering suggestions for tourist destinations, or overseeing hotel reservations. With this practical approach, students gain confidence in their ability to use English in professional settings and are ready for careers in the tourist sector, where clear communication is essential.

CONCLUSION

English proficiency is essential for professionals working in the tourism sector to communicate with and comprehend the demands of visitors. English-language instruction on industry-specific terminology and vocabulary relevant to tourism management helps students grasp concepts, trends, and best practices.

To effectively communicate their ideas, proposals, and research findings to a broader audience, experts in tourist management must possess proficient writing abilities in English. By incorporating these techniques into your teaching, you can help students in the tourism and hotel management faculty develop their communicative competence and prepare them for successful careers in the industry.

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